

IMPACT ANALYSIS AND USER EXPERIENCE

Evaluation of the Metadata Portfolio

CESSDA Metadata Management (CMM) Project
Deliverable D5
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Irena Vipavc Brvar, Irena Bolko (UL-ADP)

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1 Introduction

CESSDA Metadata Management (CMM) Project gathers the project leader - FSD and seven CESSDA partners - ADP, CASD, DDA, GESIS, NSD, SND, and UKDS. The goal of the project is to develop, promote and implement a standardised metadata design, content and practice for all CESSDA data assets. The outcome of the project - CESSDA Metadata Standards Portfolio - is scheduled to be implemented as the standard for all Service Providers within CESSDA.

The Portfolio aims to support resource discovery, question banks, preservation and data access. Furthermore, it helps all Service Providers meet the Data Seal of Approval certification requirements related to metadata issues. Support to the description of data will go beyond the social sciences, as the Portfolio benefits other disciplines as well (for example, humanities and health sciences). Its support to multilingual searches and data discovery reflects the needs of both Service Providers and researchers. Moreover, the Portfolio would enable Service Providers to retain independence as well as to interact within an integrated CESSDA service, while at the same time contributing to the commensurability of metadata and building a well-functioning discovery system.

The Portfolio includes core metadata model and controlled vocabularies (CVs) for relevant metadata fields, the latter enabling the implementation of the cross-language information retrieval systems. Whenever possible, existing CVs are used. The Portfolio covers study-level metadata and variable/question level metadata. It is standard based and compliant with Data Documentation Initiative (DDI), international standard for describing statistical and social science data. It is also extensible, enables updates and adaptations to changing functional requirements over time. The Portfolio Version 1 covers most urgent needs, primary it supports building of the Product and Service Catalogue and the Euro Question Bank.

Deliverable 5 concludes Phase 1 of the CMM project by reporting the results of the impact analysis that was conducted by ADP. It also provides pathway for the further work on the development of the Portfolio in Phase 2 of the project.

2 Objectives

The main objective of this task was to analyse the impact of the proposed portfolio solution. Portfolio Version 1 took into consideration needs of the Product and Service Catalogue and the Euro Question Bank, as well as daily workflow of the SPs. CESSDA Service Providers as Portfolio's primary users gave feedback and expressed their reservations towards the model. Adjusted System Usability Scale was applied to measure how SPs perceive usability of the Portfolio. The information we gathered provides valuable feedback for finalising the Portfolio.

3 Methodology

3.1 *Participating members*

All of currently 15 CESSDA members were invited to participate in the evaluation survey:

- **Austria (AuSSDA – The Austrian Social Science Data Archive – in establishment),**
- **Belgium (SOHDA – Social Sciences and Humanities Data Archive – preparatory phase project for sustainable archiving and sharing of research data in the humanities),**
- **Czech Republic (CSDA – Czech Social Science Data Archive),**

- **Denmark (DDA – Danish Data Archive),**
- **Finland (FSD – Finnish Social Science Data Archive),**
- **France (PROGEDO Research Infrastructure),**
- **Germany (GESIS – Leibniz Institute for the Social Sciences),**
- **Greece (So.Da.Net – Greek research infrastructure for the social sciences),**
- **Lithuania (LiDA – Lithuanian Data Archive for Humanities and Social Sciences),**
- **Netherlands (DANS – Data Archiving and Networked Services),**
- **Norway (NSD – Norwegian Centre for Research Data),**
- **Slovenia (ADP – Social Science Data Archives),**
- **Sweden (SND – Swedish National Data Service),**
- **Switzerland (FORS – Swiss Centre of Expertise in the Social Sciences) and**
- **United Kingdom (UKDS – UK Data Service).**

It should be noted that Austrian AuSSDA continues the work of Austria's previous archive – WISDOM and is overtaking its workflow processes and data. Hence, they were able to provide information about their current status of metadata documentation and what were their plans for the future.

Belgian SOHDA is in its early stages (being pilot project of BELSPO - Belgian Federal Science Policy¹) and through desktop research of their web site² we were not able to access the datasets. BELSPO, however, offers two databases of research projects³. The organization was also invited to provide an overview of their metadata structures and activities, but we did not receive any reply.

In most of the SPs that are part of CMM1 project, evaluation was conducted by employee that had not been primary involved in preparation of portfolio. In this regard, evaluator had no prior knowledge from the phase of developing the Portfolio and was thus assumed to have smaller prejudice in reporting on how current practice matched the portfolio.

Furthermore, we included additional stakeholder that expressed interest to participate in the evaluation, namely French **depositor CDSP - Centre de Données Socio-Politiques** from Sciences Po, which is one of the four partners that distributes data on the Réseau Quetelet portal (French data provider).

Adding to the complexity of analysis, we included **Dataverse** as a tool. Our aim was to evaluate if it was suitable for archiving and presenting data. The question that we addressed was: Does Dataverse offer sufficient DDI fields that match the CESSDA Portfolio's mandatory fields? DANS provided answers for that part.

In total, 15 organizations were thus included in the evaluation, and a DataVerse tool.

3.2 Survey questionnaire

Evaluation was divided in three parts. In Phase 1 of the project we did a detailed evaluation of the Mandatory elements of the Portfolio and general evaluation of the Portfolio as a whole. In Phase 2, that is scheduled for 1.5.2017 – 31.12.2018, more detailed evaluation will be made and usage outside current SPs will be taken into consideration.

¹ <http://www.belspo.be/>

² <http://www.vub.ac.be/demography/research/sohda/>

³ http://www.belspo.be/belspo/research/data_en.stm

In the first part of the survey, evaluation of the Mandatory elements (see Appendix 1), the elements, which are crucial for understanding and finding studies, was done. Chosen elements meet the Product and Service Catalogue requirements. We were interested in whether organizations were already using the elements proposed in the Portfolio or they were planning to implement them in the near future. For the elements that have defined DDI Controlled vocabulary structure, we encouraged SPs to let us know if they were using it, or if they were using their own structure. Furthermore, we asked SPs to estimate the availability of mandatory metadata in English. Participating organizations were particularly encouraged to provide comments on the usage of the elements, in order to contribute to the development of the Portfolio.

The second part of the survey was general evaluation of the Portfolio as a whole. We applied the System Usability Scale (SUS; Brooke, 1986⁴), where we adopted the original scale statements to fit the evaluation of the Portfolio (see Appendix 2). Respondents marked with “x” the box under the number which best expressed their opinion regarding each of the 11 statements. 5-point scale was used, where 1 indicated strong disagreement and 5 indicated strong agreement with the statement.

In the last part of the survey we were interested in to what extend SPs provide metadata (see Appendix 3), in particular, if they provide data on the level of study description, variable description and question text. We were also interested if this applies for their complete holdings and to what extend metadata is provided in English language.

3.3 Survey administration

On the February 8th 2017, invitation to comment the Portfolio draft was posted on the Basecamp – Service Providers’ Forum. Members of the forum are employees of 15 SPs. Portfolio itself was published as Delivery 3 of this project. Service providers were thus able to get acquainted with the Portfolio in advance and they could have posted questions and comments before the invitation for its evaluation was send out.

Personalized email invitations (one for each SP) with a link to the Google Docs Excel document, containing three spreadsheets that were used for evaluation (Mandatory Elements, General Evaluation and Providing Metadata), were sent out on February 24th, upon identifying the contact person(s) in each of the participating organizations, and replies were requested by March 10th. By that time, 7 participating organizations responded to the survey, although some of the organizations asked for additional clarifications and thus some data was missing. On March 13th we sent reminders to 10 participating organizations that had not provided the answers. We explained the importance of the feedback for the further development of the Metadata portfolio and extended the deadline for submitting the replies until March 17th. With the reminder letter we managed to collect additional 5 responses. On March 24th, we started with establishing more personal contacts with the remaining 5 organizations that we had not heard from. In the meantime, we were also in contact with the organizations that had not fully completed the evaluation form, mainly due to some ambiguities they had found in the survey. We tried to further explain the tasks and questions. By April 10th we collected 15 completed surveys and 1 evaluation of the tool, while 1 participating organizations did not reply to any of our emails.

4 Results of the survey

For clearer understanding of the use of English language in study descriptions, interpretation of the last, more general part of the survey is presented first.

⁴ <https://hell.meiert.org/core/pdf/sus.pdf>

4.1 Providing Metadata

In the third part of the evaluation survey we were interested in how extensive is currently provided metadata. SPs were asked if they provide English and national language metadata for all surveys in their holdings (see Appendix 3) and if they provide it on the level of study description, variable description and question text.

Results (Table 4.1) show that almost all service providers have study description metadata available in their national language, with the exception of one, reporting that they only use DC fields⁵. The majority of the participating organizations also reported that they provide variable description and question text in metadata. However, some of the SPs only provide them for selected studies that are available through Nesstar. Some reported that variable descriptions are available in codebooks, which are stored alongside the data as a file; the language is not standardized and it depends on the survey. If a SP provides variable description metadata, it by the rule provides question metadata as well; except in the case of one SP where this is planned.

Availability of metadata in English is less prevalent, although most of the respondents reported to have study description available in English. Variable description is provided by approximately half of the participating organizations, while English question text is even less available – provided by approximately one third of the organizations. However, as the additional comments revealed, metadata in English is not provided for all the studies. There are differences from one SP to another. Study description in English might be provided for 10 – 30% of the holdings. One SP reported that they have study description available in English, but they usually do not translate variable description and question text, unless principal investigator provides them with documentation and data files in English; another reported that translation of variables is done on request only.

Table 4.1: Providing metadata

	Available in national language (n=15)	Available in English (n=14)
Study description in metadata	15	11
Variable description in metadata	13	7
Question text in metadata	12	5

Source: Impact analysis survey, 2017

We should point out that answers on the metadata provision are not completely reliable. It seems that most of the respondents provide descriptions in English only for a part of studies, e.g. three respondents replied “Yes” (out of 14) under “Study description”, but stated in comments that it is available only for a portion of studies; similar observation can be made for “Variable description” with 6 respondents (out of 7) and for “Question text” with all 5 respondents who replied “Yes”, but according to the comments, English descriptions are not available for all the studies. This implies that percentage of metadata available in English is even lower.

4.2 Mandatory Elements

As mentioned in the previous chapter, only mandatory elements of the Portfolio were included in the evaluation survey. For each of them we asked respondents, whether they have them available in their national language (Figure 4.1) and in English (Figure 4.2) and if they are using controlled vocabularies.

⁵ <http://www.dublincore.org/documents/dces/>

Title Study (1.2)

All SP use Title of the study, yet not all offer English translation (apart from the national language). As we reported in previous chapter, not all SP offer study descriptions of their complete holdings in English. Regardless of this, most SPs are at least planning to have title available in English. ISO code for language is rarely used.

Question that arose:

- Is the field repeatable? International or multilingual studies might have more titles.

Principal Investigator Reference (1.3.1) and Publisher (1.4)

Similarly, principle investigator (PI) reference and publisher are mainly provided by almost all participating organizations. However, in all mentioned instances, free text is used and not reference ID. Some SPs are considering using different registry systems, like ORCID, ISNI⁶ or CRIS.

Fields are often not translated in English.

Questions that arose:

- Which registry system is going to be used / proposed? Should we be able to use multiple (national, international)?
- What do we do with PI that don't have "their number" (students, retired professors)?
- There is a need to use this fields for persons and organizations.
- DataCite use exact, and a bit different description of this field and its attributes. Do we need it for CESSDA?
- Do we need English translation of the names of organizations?

Publication Date (1.5)

SPs in general use Publication Date. Four of them mentioned that they are using Creation date for citation. Also, in most of the cases fields are available in English.

Questions that arose:

- Decision if Publication date or Creation date is to be used for citation and among mandatory fields. Clear definition of each field is needed.
- Proposal is to use ISO 860, but it supports many structures. Are we limiting ourselves only to years? In monthly / daily surveys it is important to have information on month and day as well (YYYY-MM-DD).

⁶ <https://www.enago.com/academy/orcid-vs-isni/>

Figure 4.1: Availability of Mandatory elements in national language (n=15)

Source: Impact analysis survey, 2017

Figure 4.2: Availability of Mandatory elements in English language (n=15)

Source: Impact analysis survey, 2017

Kind of Data (1.6)

Most of the SPs use this element, but according to the comments SPs gave, it seems that they use it in different ways. Two SPs said they don't use this element but they could produce it with information that they have on a study. Comments also implied this mandatory element is in some SPs used on the level of dataset, and not on study level. There are reports on DataCite using the element "resourceTypeGeneral"⁷ for this field, which is mandatory and not repeatable, but CV of DataCite differ from DDI CV. One SP uses DCMI-TYPE CV⁸. Only 3 SPs use DDI CV, additional 4 use their own CV. Most of the SPs that use CV for this element have its translation in English language.

Questions that arose:

- Which CV will CESSDA support? DDI (and DataCite) or will we develop our own?
- Clear definition of this element is needed!
- Will the element be defined on the level of study or dataset? If on study it needs to be repeatable.

Class Identifier (1.12.1) and Classification System name (1.12.2)

Respondents experienced some difficulties with understanding what do class identifier and classification system name refer to, thus we additionally try to communicate and explain the meaning of the field. Results show that several countries do not provide these metadata. If SP use the element, it is likely that CV is used and content is translated in English. Most of the SPs said they do not use CV for this element, and for those that do, it is not necessary that CESSDA Topic Classification is used.

Questions that arose:

- Will CESSDA Topic Classification be published on public place and made mandatory?
- Which of the elements is really mandatory? In the Portfolio also main element 1.12 Classification is marked as mandatory, and need for PaSC.

Study Area Country (1.15)

Most of the organizations are using this element and are already using or planning to use ISO code for study area country. However, some prefer to use "Spatial coverage" or "Geographical space". SPs reported that by default most surveys are done inside one country. Lower level elements are needed such as "Geographical coverage" or "Geographical unit" where one could define region or town where survey took place.

Questions that arose:

- Most studies are done inside one country. Lower level elements (region, town) are needed for classification of the study and statistical analysis of collected data.
- Mentioning 2 letter codes implies that the intention is to use ISO3166-1 Alpha 2. How will countries that no longer exists (covered under ISO3166-3) be handled?

Universe (1.16)

⁷ http://schema.datacite.org/meta/kernel-3/doc/DataCite-MetadataKernel_v3.1.pdf

⁸ <http://dublincore.org/documents/2000/07/11/dcmi-type-vocabulary/>

Almost all of the SPs use this element. With exception of one SP, this is free text field. However, some SPs reported that element is used on the level of dataset and not study.

Question that arose:

- Will the element be defined on the level of study or dataset? If on study, it needs to be repeatable.

Type of Sampling Procedure (1.18.2.1)

Element is used and translated in English in one third of SPs. Three SPs reported using DDI CV and additional two stated that are using their own CV. Otherwise CV was not reported to be used for this element.

Questions that arose:

- Will the element be defined on the level of study or dataset? If on study it needs to be repeatable.
- DDI CV does not fully cover qualitative studies methodology concepts. This implies need for additional categories.

Type of Mode Collection (1.18.4)

We can observe similar situation to the one reported with the previous metadata element - Type of Sampling Procedure. Element is commonly used, but not always translated in English. It seems that few more SPs use CV for this element. Some use DDI CV, while other use their own.

Questions that arose:

- Will the element be defined on the level of study or dataset? If on study it needs to be repeatable.
- DDI CV does not fully cover qualitative studies, neither administrative nor social data. Additional categories are needed.

Data Access (1.20)

All SPs use this element. Translation in English is available for one third of SP. Comments given for this field show that SPs are looking for more than just two levels of access that was proposed (open, restricted). Restrictions differ in relation to users and their purpose of use, and in relation to data. Different access conditions are commonly given to official administrative data then to research data.

Question that arose:

- CESSDA Access Policy⁹ was accepted by SPs in 2016. Does it provides a ground for more exhaustive classification of access restrictions and conditions?

Type of the study documentation (11.1) and Producer of the study documentation (11.2)

These are the elements that are used by about half of SPs. Those that use the element, have its English translation as well.

Arguments were given regarding the description of the element. Why it differs from the description of the element Title study (1.2)?

⁹ <https://cessda.net/content/download/963/8608/file/CESSDA%20Data%20Access%20Policy.pdf>

Question that arose:

- Is this repeatable for cases where the Producer and the Archive share creation responsibility?

Differences between SPs

One of the goals of the evaluation survey was also to compare if more developed SPs differ from less developed ones in regard to their responses to the survey. We grouped countries in two groups: developed countries (Denmark, Finland, Germany, Netherlands, Norway, Sweden, Switzerland, United Kingdom) and middle developed countries (Austria, Czech Republic, France, Greece, Lithuania, Slovenia).

Placement was done on the basis of the number of employees and maturity level of the organization that was evaluated in CESSDA SAW project¹⁰ in WP3. Archives included in the middle developed group are in most cases youngest archives, which had more classifications, guidance and examples available when they started building their collections. We didn't observed any major differences between both groups, but it seems that middle developed SPs offer more content for mandatory elements and more are also translated in English, compared to the developed SPs.

Evaluation provided by data depositor

We find the results of French data depositor evaluation encouraging. It seems that they are using most mandatory elements of the portfolio and can provide information for the missing ones if needed. At the moment they are not using Controlled vocabularies for the elements, but could classify their content. However, they don't translate content in English, this task is performed by SP.

Evaluation of the tool – Dataverse

SPs have to be able to provide metadata, but they need a tool to support their activity, preferably freely available. We took a closer look at the Dataverse Project from Harvard University. It is "an open source software application to share, cite and archive data. Dataverse provides a robust infrastructure for data stewards to host and archive data, while offering researchers an easy way to share and get credit for their data."¹¹ There are currently 2.143 Dataverse instances in the World that offers almost 49.000 datasets. The community is growing and it seems to have stable development and support team.

DANS, at the moment, the only CESSDA SP that uses Dataverse, considers that Dataverse would easily fit the needs of SP which require a data repository. Dataverse is currently covering many of the mandatory fields of the Portfolio and will in the near future be able to cover all of them. Dataverse currently supports bilingual presentations, although DANS does not have experience with this themselves. Since the community of users is rapidly growing outside of the primary English speaking community (the USA), multilingualism is one of the important task on the developers' to do list. In the current Dataverse template for Social Sciences and Humanities DDI Controlled vocabularies are not offered but could be added via API. Information on provided documents is basic but more content could be added as well. DANS's evaluation shows that with some minor modification, Dataverse could be used as a tool for acquiring, archiving and presenting / visualizing metadata and data. As part of the CESSDA SAW project, WP 4, a number of SP are assessing and testing the capabilities and usefulness of Dataverse for their own diverse needs. However, modifications that are related to the specific requirements of an individual (or group of) CESSDA SP will most likely need to develop by themselves, or as part of a workplan project; for the CESSDA 2018 workplan a Dataverse proposal will be submitted to work on these modifications.

¹⁰ <http://cessdasaw.eu/deliverables/>

¹¹ <http://dataverse.org/>

4.1 General Evaluation

For the general evaluation part of the survey we applied the System Usability Scale (SUS; Brooke, 1986). Three of the participating organizations were not able to provide the answers completely as they found the statements unclear and difficult to relate them to the Portfolio situation.

According to the results (Figure 4.3), participating organizations expressed generally positive attitude towards usage of the Portfolio. They found it rather easy to use and that the elements in the Portfolio mainly cover the elements in their current study description. Respondents did not report on any major shortcomings of the Portfolio and also expressed belief that not much additional support (either from co-workers or from CESSDA or other SPs) would be requested. Comments on all elements of the whole Portfolio were gathered separately so we expected just general evaluation to be provided here.

Comparing middle and developed SPs, there is a clearly seen difference (Figure 4.3), that middle developed SPs will require more help of CESSDA MO and reported they will need some more time to learn how to use the Portfolio. The first version of the description of the Portfolio elements was written with regard to the DDI Lifecycle, which is, however, not yet commonly used in all SPs. A suggestion was made to prepare descriptions and coding also for DDI Codebook. In general, developed SPs are more self-confident, although this does not apply to everyone. Comments imply that some SPs will need time to adjust their workflow and systems to the Portfolio. The use of software for distribution of studies is also crucial for the use of Portfolio. If software, such as Nesstar and Dataverse, will not support the use of the Portfolio elements, at least mandatory ones, then this will be an issue needed to be taken into consideration.

existing content to the proposed ones. English translation of elements is not used systematically, as well as few Controlled vocabularies that currently exist. It is up to CESSDA to define to what extent SPs will need to provide metadata in agreed structure. This evaluation can help to reconsider the need of each of them. After deciding on content of metadata, the transition period will need to be provided for SP's to meet the requirements. Our evaluation confirm that all SPs will be able to follow the minimum specification of the metadata, which requires some minor revisions only in order to resolve the remaining questions.

Even though Portfolio is based on DDI specification that all SPs use, it is clear that the usage of elements and Controlled vocabularies of the elements still differ between SPs. SPs are looking for clear guidance, definitions of the elements (e.g. is the element repeatable or not, does it has CV and which, its proposed length if free text field is used), and would appreciate examples that would ease their work. In relation to this, unique IDs for each element in CV and extension of classification to qualitative, administrative and social data are needed. For the 'Middle developed countries' which are usually not able to invest into its custom made tools this could be achieved also with the reference to the common tools development and evaluation of existing tools. Quality controlled metadata creation can be supported with the common tools, containing template for the CESSDA requirements.

Appendix 1: Evaluation of mandatory elements

No.	Mandatory Element	Mandatory	Content of the element available in national language	Content of the element available in English	CV for this element	Usage of Controlled Vocabularies	Comments
1.1	Study Number	M	Yes/No/Planned	Yes/No/Planned	NO		
1.2	Title Study	M	Yes/No/Planned	Yes/No/Planned	<u>Use ISO 3166 2-letter code as countrypairs: language - country, as attribute information (e.g. DE-DE, or DE-AT)</u>	Yes ISO/Plan to use ISO/ Yes my own CV/No	
1.3.1	Principle Investigator Reference	M	Yes/No/Planned	Yes/No/Planned	NO	Yes/No/Planned	
1.4	Publisher	M (for PasC)	Yes/No/Planned	Yes/No/Planned	NO	Yes/No/Planned	
1.5	Publication Date	M (for PaSC)	Yes/No/Planned	Yes/No/Planned	<u>ISO 8601</u>	Yes ISO/Plan to use ISO/ Yes my own CV/No	
2.6	Kind of Data	M (for PaSC)	Yes/No/Planned	Yes/No/Planned	<u>http://www.ddialliance.org/Specification/DDI-CV/KindOfDataFormat_1.0.html</u>	Yes DDI CV/Plan to use DDI CV/Yes my own CV/No	
1.12.1	Class Identifier	M	Yes/No/Planned	Yes/No/Planned	NO	Yes/No/Planned	
1.12.2	Classification System Name	M	Yes/No/Planned	Yes/No/Planned	NO	Yes/No/Planned	
1.15	Study Area Country	M (for PaSC)	Yes/No/Planned	Yes/No/Planned	<u>ISO 3166 2-letter code.</u>	Yes ISO/Plan to use ISO/ Yes my own CV/No	
1.16	Universe	M	Yes/No/Planned	Yes/No/Planned	NO	Yes/No/Planned	
1.18.2.1	Type of Sampling Procedure	M (for PasC)	Yes/No/Planned	Yes/No/Planned	<u>DDI CV: SamplingProcedure</u>	Yes DDI CV/Plan to use DDI CV/Yes my own CV/No	
1.18.4	Type of Mode Collection	M (for PaSC)	Yes/No/Planned	Yes/No/Planned	<u>DDI CV: ModeOfCollection</u>	Yes DDI CV/Plan to use DDI CV/Yes my own CV/No	
1.20.1	Data access	M (forPaSC)	Yes/No/Planned	Yes/No/Planned	CV "AccessClass" - CV by CMMgroup - contains only "open" and "restricted"	Yes/No/Planned	
11.1	Title of study documentation	M	Yes/No/Planned	Yes/No/Planned	NO	Yes/No/Planned	
11.2	Producer of the study documentation	M	Yes/No/Planned	Yes/No/Planned	NO	Yes/No/Planned	

Appendix 2: General evaluation of the Portfolio

Listed below are the statements describing experience of using the Portfolio. Please mark X under the number which best expresses your opinion regarding the statement.

		Strongly disagree				Strongly agree
	Statement	1	2	3	4	5
1	I think we will bring the Portfolio into use.					
2	I found the Portfolio unnecessarily complex.					
3	I thought the Portfolio was easy to use.					
4	I think that I would need the support of a coworker to be able to use the Portfolio.					
5	I think that we would need support from CESSDA MO or other SPs to be able to use the Portfolio.					
6	I found the elements in the Portfolio cover the elements in our current study description.					
7	I thought there was too much inconsistency in the Portfolio.					
8	I would imagine that most people would learn to use the Portfolio very quickly.					
9	I found the Portfolio very cumbersome to use.					
10	I feel very confident about implementing the Portfolio in our organisation.					
11	I would need to learn a lot of things before I could get going with the Portfolio.					

* Modified version of the System Usability Scale (SUS; Brooke, 1986)

Appendix 3: Level of Providing metadata

	Are you currently providing metadata on the level of:	Content of the element available in national language	Content of the element available in English	Comment
1	Study description	Yes/No/Planned	Yes/No/Planned	
2	Variable description	Yes/No/Planned	Yes/No/Planned	
3	Question text	Yes/No/Planned	Yes/No/Planned	

CESSDA AS
CESSDA House

Parkveien 20
5007 Bergen
NORWAY

phone: +47 55 58 36 48
e-mail: cessda@cessda.net
www.cessda.net